

TEACHERS' RESOURCES IN EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION: CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIES

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Teachers' Resources in Early Childhood Education: Challenges and Strategies

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Abstract

This study investigated the challenges faced by the teachers in early childhood education regarding educational resources and explored potential strategies to address the challenges. This study was conducted with 10 early childhood education teachers from an urban school located in District 1, Zamboanga City. The results indicated that most teachers faced challenges in accessing educational materials due to the limited availability of the educational resources. To address these challenges, teachers often use personal money to provide the materials and collaborate with other organizations and external stakeholders that are willing to support the student education. These stakeholders include parents, the local community, nearby establishments and local government units. In conclusion, teachers' experienced financial constraints, technological challenges, embarrassment and communication barriers that exacerbate the situation by preventing resource acquisition, partnerships and complicate teaching practices. Positive collaboration experiences highlight the importance of community support, while negotiating parental perceptions and developing effective communication channels emerge as critical strategies. This study recommends that early childhood education curriculum developer should ensure a variety of materials are easily accessible, collaborate with technology specialists, and collaborate with school officials. Future researchers should explore the challenges and strategies in accessing educational materials between the context of private and public schools.

Keywords: *access to educational materials, strategies, partnership and collaboration, teachers' resources*

Introduction

Early childhood education (ECE) plays a vital role in the cognitive, social, emotional, and physical development of young children. It is widely recognized as a crucial foundation for lifelong learning and success. However, lack of resources within the area of early childhood education is a persistent and global challenge that slows down the delivery of quality education and limits the potential of countless children. The availability of resources is a crucial aspect of the childhood environment that determines a child's quality of life (Hota & Barch, 2019).

Lack of enough material resources is one of the causes of unsuccessful instruction. Major reforms that bring the highest level of quality, equity, and integrity to the system are necessary to close the gap between the existing state of learning outcomes and what is needed (National Education Policy, 2020).

ECE teachers at Guiwan Elementary School encounter similar challenges, such as a lack of resources, language barriers, and behavioral issues. Teachers have highlighted the challenges of limited resources when it comes to teaching in public schools, particularly in far-flung areas, making it challenging to meet all of the students' needs. Many underprivileged areas lack access to important learning materials such as books, teaching aids, classroom supplies, and even adequate learning spaces, which limit successful lesson delivery.

Research shows that early childhood education has a significant impact on children's future academic success and social development. Studies have repeatedly investigated teachers' resource challenges in many nations, concentrating on difficulty developing learning materials, insufficient classroom resources, and the selection of appropriate teaching as well as learning tools. However, limited research delved into these challenges in the Philippines. The pressing need to address these issues is further emphasized by the role of teachers in developing young learners' foundational skills. When teachers do not have access to sufficient resources, the quality of education provided to children is significantly compromised, affecting their long-term learning.

This study seeks to delve deeper into the challenges posed by the lack of resources and explore effective strategies to improve the quality and accessibility of early childhood education (ECE) programs. Identifying the specific challenges faced by teachers in resource-limited settings and examining successful strategies employed in overcoming these barriers, the study aims to contribute valuable insights about practical solutions. Teachers' strategies can better equip young students with the skills and opportunities they need to thrive in the future. Addressing these challenges will improve the current condition of ECE and ensure a more equitable and inclusive education.

The study focused to determine the challenges and different strategies of teachers' resources in terms of access to educational materials, partnerships and collaboration in early childhood education teachers in Guiwan Elementary School. The study was qualitative research that collected data through an interview among ten (10) selected early childhood education teachers in Guiwan Elementary School. It covers on challenges and different strategies and there will be no concrete solutions formulated in this study. Also it aimed to find out the teachers' lived experiences in coping the challenges amidst constraint of teachers' resources. It does not cover the funding of teachers' resources. The findings of the study are only applicable in Guiwan Elementary School and may not be applicable in other

educational settings.

Research Questions

This qualitative research aimed to investigate the multifaceted issues surrounding teachers' resources in early childhood education and explore potential strategies to solve these challenges. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions.

1. What are the challenges associated with teachers' resources in early childhood education in terms of:
 - 1.1. access to educational materials; and
 - 1.2. partnerships and collaboration?
2. What are the strategies used to overcome challenges about the Teachers' Resources in terms of:
 - 2.1. access to educational materials; and
 - 2.2. partnerships and collaboration?

Literature Review

Early Childhood Education

According to Alvarado (2023) early childhood education refers to the period of time from a child's birth to when they enter kindergarten. It is also a very important time of the child's lives because in early childhood education it helps the students or the learners to be prepared in a formal set up of the education. Children tend to learn how to interact with others, including their peers, teachers, and parents. University of Massachusetts Global defines early childhood education as the official term for teaching the young kids and formal and informal educational programs that guides the growth and development for the children throughout their preschool years specifically from birth to five years old.

All children have equal access to and requirements for kindergarten education thanks to Republic Act No. 10157, also called the kindergarten. Education Act. In light of this, the Department of Education (DepEd) publishes the enclosed Omnibus Policy on Kindergarten Education for the 2016–2017 academic year as well as any upcoming years.

Therefore, this DepEd Order (DO) establishes the fundamental requirements for a successful implementation of the Kindergarten Education Program in both public and private schools across the country. It also serves as the foundation for the accreditation and/or recognition of those who want to establish early learning centers.

Early childhood education programs tend to be the preparation for the learners to their primary school, it also aims the developmental milestones of the child such as social, emotional, cognitive, and physical needs to build a strong foundation for lifelong learning (UNESCO, 2023).

LinkedIn (2023) highlighted the nine (9) problems faced in early childhood education such as access and equity, quality disparities, parental awareness, standardization, teacher training, lack of play, united government involvement, infrastructure and safety, resource scarcity and language barrier. These problems became the central issue of the early childhood education because it really has a big impact on the children development, as this study continues the researchers will provide other information or problems that will be stated of the participants of this study.

Teachers' Resources in Early Childhood Education

According to Safeopedia (2018) refers to the shortage of commodities needed to sustain life or a specific standard of living. Economic theory constantly struggles with the issue of resource constraints because it frequently assumes that people have limitless demands but must find ways to satisfy them by utilizing finite resources. It is also stated that the inability to obtain the items required to maintain activities or a specific standard of activity is known as a scarcity of resources. For both students and teachers, a lack of resources in the classroom can be extremely distressing. The lack of adequate resources not only causes the students and teachers distress, but also prevents them from learning to their fullest potential. As soon as we are aware of these issues, we can start looking into solutions to this challenging issue (Maffea, 2020).

Access to Educational Materials

Vice President and Secretary of Education Sarah Duterte (2023) claims that the most urgent problem facing Philippine education is a lack of resources and school facilities to enable the optimal teaching procedure (CNN Philippines, 2023).

Fiddiman et al., (2021) Students can access resources as needed. All learners should have easy access to learning resources and be given the freedom to use them as needed. In relation to our study, this access to educational resources is one of the necessities to avoid resource constraints. Students in early childhood education will gain a lot by having access to educational resources, as well as the entire educational system. In addition to benefiting from their current educational experience, early childhood education children who have access to educational resources will also have a brighter, more just, and better future. It equips individuals for ongoing learning and development.

In addition to locations with significant levels of poverty, middle class communities also exhibit a lack of resources. Because it is

difficult for schools to pay for brand-new laptops for every kid, teachers in the classroom must find a way to make up for that. If they run out of textbooks, that could imply they use a projector to let the students see the teacher's screen. Despite the tasks assigned to them, inadequate resources in schools have a severe negative impact on students' learning and teachers' ability to instruct (Maffea, 2020). Furthermore, inadequate supply of resource items, such as white boards, charts, posters, blocks, cards, clay, crayons, and chalk (Herward, 2009).

Partnerships and Collaboration

Partnerships between schools and the local community are relationships that are developed via cooperation. These collaborations are crucial for fostering a climate that is encouraging and nurturing for learners to learn and develop. Additionally, they give schools access to local resources and knowledge to enhance student wellbeing, school fundraising, and educational quality. Partnerships between the school and the community are crucial for fostering an atmosphere in which students may learn and succeed. These collaborations give schools access to a wide range of resources, knowledge, and assistance that can help them meet the needs of their students and families. (Barnes, 2023).

According to Almaguer (2021) Student success is based on collaborative educational partnerships. Schools must engage and communicate with families and communities as student populations become more diverse in order to narrow the gap between home and school. Being connected to other institutions and organizations can help schools get the right and sufficient resources. In relation to our study, collaboration and partnerships with other institutions and organizations can help reduce resource constraint. Actions and understandings from one context reinforce, support, and add to those in other settings, and relationships are formed between the educational institution and the home and community (Mitchell et. al., 2018).

It is one of the strategies that the teachers use to reach the parents of the learners. Most preschools are not equipped with the right tools which is why many of the children are having a question or hanging ideas of a particular thing because the child did not expose to the right materials (Illumine Labs, 2019).

Challenges in Early Childhood Education

According to Childcare Education Institute (2022) early childhood educators have faced a number of challenges since the inception of organized childcare. Many of the problems that early childhood education teachers are currently facing are not brand-new.

Access to Educational Materials

The majority of public schools still don't have the textbook to student ratio that is mandated, according to research conducted by an advocacy group for education (CNN Philippine, 2023).

Most preschools are not equipped with the right tools which is why many of the children are having a question or hanging ideas of a particular thing because the child did not expose to the right materials (Illumine Labs, 2019). This implies that teachers do not have adequate teaching and learning resources and there is a big impact to child's growth because the child is not exposed to the materials, (Writers Bureau Centre (WBC), 2023).

Partnerships and Collaboration

Partnerships are motivated by shared objectives, mutual trust, respect, and a dedication to enhancing educational results for students. Additionally, by uniting various community resources, these collaborations hope to create a more encouraging, stimulating, and inclusive learning environment. (NMSI's, 2023). To overcome these challenges, it is essential to establish clear goals, open lines of communication, and shared decision-making processes. In relation to our study, partnership and collaboration can halt the challenges in resource constraint. Teachers can collaborate and can access educational materials through sponsorships.

LinkedIn (2023) highlighted these challenges require collaborative efforts between the government, educational institutions, communities, and parents so that we can know that our learners are improving or still adjusting.

Districts also clearly voiced their appreciation of the importance of relationships and collaboration among key stakeholders who touched the lives of children enrolled in the grantee districts. (Alverson et. al., 2019). It is also highlighted in the study of Illumine Labs (2019), that clear and transparent parent communication is another essential responsibility of the early education teachers.

Programs should engage parents more actively. In a case like this, the parents can help and contribute to the school to provide what are the necessities for the child's experience in the school and to provide them with the materials they need (Lynch, 2023).

Early Childhood Teacher Strategies

Teachers across the country are working hard to provide children with the skills they need to succeed in the twenty-first century. Teachers must nurture suitable teaching methodologies and enabling learning settings that stimulate critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving in their students in addition to instilling in them the flexibility to rapidly adjust to changing technology (Reinen, 2019). Teaching strategies, in their broadest definition, refer to the structure, system, methods, techniques, procedures, and processes that a teacher employs throughout instruction. These are the tactics used by the teacher to help students learn. The teacher must consider the

learners' age, level, class setting, class length, and content. To reach all students with varied learning styles, the instructor may employ a variety of instructional aides to reach all pupils with different learning styles and abilities (Heinrich, 2017).

Reinan (2023), stated that teachers provide the children's needs and what they need to succeed in the twenty-first century. It is also added by the idea of Munholland (2023), that strategies were created to use in teaching to help children in their developmental phase. In addition to this Study.com (2023) added a method that teachers use in teaching where it keeps students engaged and it helps the students to practice and develop their different skills.

According to Thompson (2017), teacher strategies have a great contribution when it comes to the efficient teaching and learning of young children in schools. Where teacher look for the best strategies that they think will suit the needs of their students, choosing the strategies that will help in the development of the child in the different developments.

Access to Educational Materials

Strategies for managing funds are essential for providing a high-quality learning environment for early childhood education students. In relation to our study, good financial management is vital in education in order to give the necessary materials in teaching and learning experiences to early childhood education teachers and learners. Teaching strategies are the approaches and procedures used by teachers to help students learn. A teacher chooses the teaching approach that is best appropriate to the students' current level of knowledge, the idea being studied, and the stage in the students' learning journey. To teach academic topics and satisfy the particular requirements of students, an effective teacher employs the most inventive and creative teaching approaches.

Resources that are tailored to each student's unique learning style including access to art materials, technology, etc. (Alcocer, 2023). Access to textbooks is an important factor in addressing what and how much they learn. Accessing educational resources like textbooks is important to know the learnings of the children, the knowledge that they have acquired (Muthanje, et, al. 2020).

Structural Learning (2022) Teaching strategies and the use of instructional materials are critical in providing high-quality experiences to all students and supporting their diverse learning styles. In our study, teaching strategies are effective, and they will provide the children with a suitable learning environment that encourages a variety of learning. Teachers must be equipped with a variety of teaching strategies in order to provide and use a variety of teaching materials in order to foster the learnings of children with varying learning styles and abilities.

Partnerships and Collaboration

A New Way Forward offers educational leaders in K-12 schools and colleges of education insight, advice, and direction on the task of forming partnerships. With these overlapping constraints and converging interests, partnerships emerge as a foundational strategy for strengthening our teachers' education (Chandler, 2021). It is critical to have a partnership and collaboration, especially among teachers, parents, and other organizations, in order to understand the challenges that learners, teachers, and schools may face. In relating to our study, the importance of partnership and collaboration is especially valuable in supporting the needs of learners and teachers in the teaching and learning experiences. Also, to strengthen teacher and school support in order to provide a quality education for students.

According to Durack (2022) working together can help the students to equip themselves with the knowledge and skills that they need to succeed in their education. This shows that partnerships and collaboration between teachers and other people who help in the education of the students can lead to success. Supporting them and giving them the needs to continue in their education with the proper resources to meet their different developmental needs. The involvement of external stakeholders is very beneficial to the educational program and school improvement because of their financial and material support (DepEd Cavite Research, 2022).

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a qualitative-phenomenological research design. It focused on the lived experiences of an individual. The qualitative method of phenomenology, according to Alhazmi and Kaufmann (2022), it is a theoretical tool for educational investigations because it enables researchers to participate in adaptable activities that can clarify and improve a better grasp of complex phenomena, like many different facets of the human social experience.

Qualitative-phenomenological research design was the most appropriate research design for this study to investigate strategies used by early childhood education teachers. It allows researchers to evaluate and understand the different aspects of human social experiences and is flexible enough to examine a wide range of research question.

Respondents

The respondents were chosen through purposive sampling. Crossman (2020) defines it as a non- probability sample that is selected depending on the goals of the study and the characteristics of the population. It's also called criticizing, discerning, or subjectively sampling. In choosing the respondents, the researchers used the fishbowl method, in which they picked 10 papers from the fishbowl. The fishbowl contains four (4) numbers of respondents that indicate a grade level inside the fishbowl for each grade level from

kindergarten to grade 3. In this method, researchers chose their respondents from all levels. If the participants are unwilling to participate, they can withdraw from the conversation.

A semi-structured interview was conducted with early childhood education teachers in an Urban School, located in District 2 Zamboanga City. Moreover, the target respondents are early childhood education teacher. There were ten (10) Early Childhood Education Teachers. The study finds out the teachers' perspectives and their experiences in addressing challenges and strategies.

Instrument

This study utilized qualitative methodology. Since the aim is to determine the challenges and strategies for dealing with the issues in teachers' resources, a semi-structured interview was used as the main data-gathering for our research. This semi-structured interview consisted of two parts with a total of six (6) items. The first part consists of three questions that covered the challenges associated with the resources of the target respondents from the urban school, located in District 2 Zamboanga City, and the second part consisted of three items that covered the respondent's strategies when dealing with the issues in teachers' resources. Additionally, to guarantee the verbal exchange was completed and provided a reliability test, and an audio recorder was employed.

Procedure

The following guidelines served as a guide for the researchers in conducting the interview:

Obtaining approval before starting a study. Researchers created and provided a formal written letter, which the researcher instructor approved, and got the consent from the principals of the schools where the study was conducted a personal interview with the chosen respondents. After the research instructor approved the letter, it was sent to the participants in advanced to request permission to perform a study at a time that works best for them.

Conduct of Personal Interview. The proper setting is done where the participants is comfortable with the way the interview was conducted. The open-ended interview was thoroughly explained the responses, and participants were guaranteed that their answers will be kept private. In addition, the participants were informed of the interview's objective, expectations, and timeline in order to prevent conflicts. With the purpose of obtaining information from the participants as much as possible, the interview was conducted informally using a conversational style guided by a set of guiding questions. One question at a time is asked to the participants that gave them enough time to ponder or formulate their responses. All information gathered were handled with the utmost confidentiality, securely stored, and used exclusively for academic purposes only. The data gathered was anonymized. If a risk arises during the one-on-one interview, the researchers-maintained composure, assessed the circumstances, and prioritized everyone's safety first. Guidelines observed while handling crises or unexpected events. If the respondents are uncomfortable during the one-on-one interview, the researchers will ask if they would still like to proceed to show respect and concern for the respondents' feelings of comfort. In any case, sensitive issues/ topics discussed during the one-on-one interview. The researchers retained respect and composure, actively listen to the respondents' viewpoints, comprehend and accepted the respondents' opinions, perspectives, and experiences, avoid making assumptions, judgments, or generalizations, assessed the situation, and provides evidence to their conclusions. Additionally, if respondents are feeling physically distressed, the researchers sought the assistance of an expert who can help handle the situation.

Data Analysis

The study employed a qualitative methodology that utilized a thematic approach to comprehensively themes and variations presented in the data. It is a method for looking at qualitative data, which involved going over a set of data and looking for patterns in how the data is interpreted to find themes (Caulfield, 2019).

Rautenbach (2021) In order to thoroughly explore relevant themes and patterns regarding the problem of teachers' resources in early childhood education, this research study employs a thematic method. The study has different themes, which are the teachers' resources, challenges in early childhood education, and early childhood education teachers' strategies. Under this, there are also the same two sub-themes: access to educational materials, partnerships, and collaboration, which was analyzed the pattern of each theme from this research study to different multiples of works through the different studies. This approach improved the depth of analysis, provides a holistic understanding of challenges and solutions such as strategies in coping with teachers' resources constrain.

Ethical Considerations

For ethical considerations, the researchers secured the full consent submission of the manuscript at Western Mindanao State University Research Ethics Committee Review Board that sought permission in the study conducted. The study complied the principle of respondent's confidentiality with respect to the rights entitled to them to be fully knowledgeable and informed of the said procedures and the details of the study ensured the participants shall not be subjected in any harm. The privacy of research participants was protected and the voluntary participation of respondents in the research was considered. Furthermore, the research participants have the right to refuse or withdraw from the study.

Results and Discussion

This section includes a section on how the findings overcome the challenges, as well as demographic information for the respondents,

data collection, analysis, and themes. This chapter shows the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of findings derived from information gathered from respondents through one-on-one interviews. This study aimed to investigate the multifaceted issues surrounding teachers' resources in early childhood education and explore potential strategies to solve these challenges.

This study was intended to get the information regarding the challenges and the strategies of the teachers they have encountered when dealing with teachers' resources. After all the ten (10) interviews were transcribed, the themes and categories emerged, the results were able to connect with the research questions. The early childhood education (ECE) teachers were asked ten (10) semi-structured questions to identify the challenges and strategies of teachers' resources.

The following interview questions were thematically organized, together with the response and ideas from the early childhood education teachers' responses to the interview questions. The challenges associated with teachers' resources in early childhood education in terms of access to educational materials with two (2) questions, the challenges in accessing to educational materials and how it affects the teaching process of the teachers would provide an answer to interview question 1.1 (I Q 1.1) and interview question 1.2 (IQ1.2) Interview question 2.1 (IQ 2.1) tackles about Partnership and collaboration in which the challenges that teachers encountered in looking For partnership and collaboration would be reflected. The strategies that were used to overcome challenges about the Teachers' Resources in terms of: Access to educational materials with two questions. The strategies that were used in accessing to educational materials and how these strategies help the teachers overcome the challenges in accessing educational materials would be provided in interview question 1.1 (IQ1.1) and interview question 1.2(IQ 1.2). The strategies that were used by the teachers to work together with other organizations and external stakeholders would be reflected in interview question 2.1 (IQ 2.1). Moreover, all the interview questions were summed up.

What are the challenges associated with teachers' resources in early childhood education in terms of:

Access to educational materials

Interview Question 1.1 What challenges did you encounter in accessing educational materials?

Seven (7) of the respondents (Teacher A, B, C, D, E, G, and J) have the same answers that focused on the challenges that they encountered when accessing educational materials, where all of them experienced the limited educational materials that are needed in catering to the needs of young learners. While one (1) of the respondents (Teacher H) doesn't feel any challenge in accessing educational materials, the teacher H utilizes the ability of technology and the internet that can support the effectiveness of its teaching.

Interview Question 1.2 How do these challenges affect your access to educational materials?

Four (4) of the respondents (Teacher A, B, C, G) experienced the same, which they discussed about time consuming when it comes to the challenges that affected their access to educational materials, they had a hard time when it comes to the preparation of the teaching materials. Three (3) of the respondents (Teacher D, E, and F) Have the same thoughts, which limit the teaching effectiveness where students had a hard time understanding or even can't understand what the lesson is all about, as well the learners become bored throughout the discussions. On the other hand, two (2) respondents (Teacher H and J) had a hard time accessing technology because they were seasoned teacher, and instead they decide to use and go back to the traditional way of teaching. One (1) respondent (Teacher I) among others don't feel any challenge in terms of technologies and providing effectiveness in teaching, because as to teacher I, teacher I is a fresh or young teacher.

Partnerships and Collaboration

Interview Question 2.1 What challenges did you encounter in looking for partnerships and collaboration?

Four of the respondents (Teachers A, B, C, and J) have the same perspective in terms of challenges encountered in looking for partnerships and collaboration, being hesitant to ask for help because of embarrassment with the parents, LGUs, and barangays. As well as the difficulty in communicating with potential partners and overcoming perceptions of begging. Two of the respondents (Teachers D and E) both lie to "Brigada Eskwela" as an opportune moment to connect with the parents and seek for partnership. Both teachers emphasized the importance of this event in facilitating contact with parents and working with GPTA officers to address concerns such as a lack of resources. Also discussed the difficulty of some parents interpreting requests for assistance as simply related to fundraising or elections, which may affect parents' desire to donate. Two of the respondents (Teachers G and H) share positive experiences with partnerships and communication. Both teachers emphasize the help received from their communities, particularly barangay leaders and parents. Underline these stakeholders' willingness to contribute aid and resources, when necessary, without experiencing significant challenges or barriers in communication. Lastly, two of the respondents (Teachers F and I) have ideals that are based on self-reliance and a reluctance to actively seek external support, particularly in terms of classroom resources. Both teachers indicate a preference for using Teachers own resources and efforts to provide for their students. Teacher F emphasizes effective communication channels and technology-enabled access to materials, whereas Teacher I acknowledges a reluctance to seek assistance owing to a fear of criticism and a belief in personal accountability for providing classroom resources. Despite their different approaches to communication and resource acquisition, both teachers emphasize their commitment to student learning and motivation.

What are the strategies used to overcome challenges about Teachers' Resources in terms of:

Access to Educational Materials

Interview Question 1.1 What are the strategies do you use in accessing educational materials?

Two (2) of the respondents (Teachers A and H) have the same answers they ask help from their colleagues to have other ideas or strategies that they will use in accessing educational materials. Four (4) of the respondents (Teachers B, C, D and E) answered they used concrete materials, printed materials and accessed the online platform to download some educational videos. One (1) of the respondents (Teacher F) answered that collaborative learning and discussion are one of the strategies that can be used in accessing educational materials. The teacher I answered then self-supporting is one of the strategies used to access educational materials. Teacher J answered that Gradual Release of Responsibility (GRR) is used as one of the strategies in accessing educational materials. One (1) of the respondents do not have the answer to the intended question.

Interview Question 1.2 How do these strategies help you overcome the challenges of accessing educational materials?

Five (5) of the respondents (Teachers B, D, E, F, and J) have the same answer: that by doing their strategies, their teaching gets easier, and they can also teach more effectively. Two (2) of the respondents (Teachers H and A) answered that their strategies for overcoming their challenges are when the parents are willing to help them by collaborating with them. One (1) of the respondents (Teacher I) responded that their strategies can aid them in teaching the students. One (1) of the respondents (Teacher G) stated that their strategies can help them “realize the objectives for the day” in the way of buying materials for teaching. One (1) respondent's (Teacher C) response was unrelated to the question.

Partnerships and Collaboration

Interview Question 2.1 What strategies do you use to work together with other organizations and external stakeholders?

Five (5) of the respondents (Teachers B, C, D, H, and I) have the same answers they use the strategy of GPTA/PTA meetings to communicate with Parents about the lack of teaching materials and parents’ volunteers to contribute to donate material. Four (4) of the respondents (Teacher E, F, G, and J) answered that they send solicitation letters to establishments in their school community and barangay officials, inviting stakeholders in the school, visiting their offices to ask for donations in teaching materials and transportation for field trips. One (1) of the

Emergent Themes and Codes

In qualitative research, coding is a common procedure and an essential component. Considering the analytical procedure and the methods by which researchers analyze their data to produce new findings.

Creswell (2015) emphasizes the importance of analyzing qualitative text data to understand its meaning and organize it in a meaningful manner.

Statement of the problem 1: What are the challenges associated with teachers’ resources in early childhood education in terms of access to educational materials, and partnerships and collaboration?

Table 1. Relationship of Interview Responses to Research Question 1

Superordinate Themes	Subordinate Themes	Codes
Resource constraints and accessibility	Teacher’s limited educational materials	Limited educational materials
		Insufficient supply of textbooks
	Lack of budget in producing educational materials	Not enough materials
		Financial constraints
	Protracted in producing educational materials	Using own money
Time constraint		
Time consuming		
Barriers to communication and collaboration	Technologically inexperienced	It takes time to prepare
		Technologically inept
	Difficulty in seeking partnerships and collaboration	Internet access
		Self dependency
		Begging
Difficulty in communicating with other organizations and external stakeholders	Difficulty in communication	
	Fear of embarrassment	
		Reluctant

Relationship of Theme 1: Challenges associated with teachers’ resources in early childhood education in terms of access to educational materials and partnerships and collaboration

The following are the challenges that early childhood teachers encounter and how the challenges impede in accessing to educational materials and partnerships and collaboration.

Teacher's limited educational materials
 Lack of budget in producing educational materials
 Protracted in producing educational materials
 Technologically inexperienced
 Difficulty in seeking partnerships and collaboration
 Difficulty in communicating with other organizations and external stakeholders

Figure 1. *Diagram of Research Question 1*

Resource Constraints and Accessibility

According to the Small Island State Report (2021), the findings of their study show that resource constraints refer to insufficient or inadequate resources such as instructional and teaching materials. It limits the accessibility of the materials to the learners because it is not enough to cater to all their needs. Moreover, because of these challenges, teachers use their own money to provide the materials they need.

Teacher's limited educational materials

The majority of educators stated that one of the difficulties they faced when instructing in early childhood education was the scarcity of instructional resources. The absence of supplies in their classroom and instructional materials for their students.

Lack of budget in producing educational materials

The teacher respond also that they can't provide educational materials to their students due to the financial or budget that are given from them. The budget is given to them is limited as they need money to support their needs in teaching as they highlight that being an early childhood education teacher, they need more teaching materials like providing a visual aids as young children's is a visual learner.

Protracted in producing educational materials

The majority of teachers mentioned how difficult it is for them to prepare educational materials and how time-consuming it is to overcome barriers that limit their access to educational resources. They think that even with limited resources, there will be enough time to prepare and have instructional materials that can offer a high- quality education.

Technology inexperienced

Some teachers find it difficult to use technology because they are seasoned educators; as a result, they choose to use the traditional method of instruction as it is where they find easy.

Barriers to Communication and collaboration

This theme focuses about the challenges that are connected to fostering partnerships and collaboration within the educational system. It highlights the difficulties in terms of establishing a successful collaboration with other organizations and external stakeholders due to communication barriers and differences in principles towards the educational process of their children. It also emphasized the importance of having an effective communication and collaboration to address the limitations of resources, enhancing and strengthening the educational outcomes of every learner (Linkedin, n.d). This collaboration and communication are abilities that exchange different information, ideas, feedback and also helps in working together towards the same common goals. These skills or abilities are very crucial especially in educational innovation, it enables leaders to engage and connect with diverse stakeholders, identify the needs and opportunities, as well as the concrete solutions.

Difficulty in seeking partnerships and collaboration

The majority of teachers share a similar viewpoint regarding the difficulties they face when seeking partnerships and collaborations, with many feelings embarrassed to approach parents, local government units, and barangays for assistance.

Difficulty in communicating with other organizations and external stakeholders

It was mentioned by a few teachers that they are finding it difficult to collaborate with parents because some of them don't have the time to talk to them or aren't supporting the goals that the teachers have set for their students. As well as the challenge of overcoming stereotypes about begging and speaking with possible partners.

Statement of the problem 2: What are the strategies used to overcome challenges about teachers' resources in terms of educational materials, and partnerships and collaboration?

Table 2. Relationship of Interview Responses to Research Question 2

Superordinate Themes	Subordinate Themes	Codes
Teachers' resources/ materials	Teacher's use of Printed Materials as strategy	Printed Materials Cut out pictures
	Teacher's use of Concrete Materials as strategy	Concrete Materials Instructional materials
	Using internet to access educational materials as strategy	Internet Access Downloadable educational videos
Communication and Collaboration	Teacher's strategy in Communicating with parents, LGUs, community.	Communicating with parents, LGUs, community Solicitation letters Brigada Eskwela PTA/GPTA conferences

Figure 2. Diagram of Research Question 2

Relationship of Theme 2: Strategies used to overcome challenges about teachers' resources in terms of educational materials, and partnerships and collaboration

The following are the strategies that the teachers in early childhood used to overcome the challenges that impedes in accessing to educational materials and partnerships and collaboration.

Teacher's use of Printed Materials as strategy

Teacher's use of Concrete Materials as strategy

Using internet to access educational materials as strategy

Teacher's strategy in Communicating with parents, LGUs, community.

Teaching resource/ materials

Smith (2023) stated that teaching resources are defined as the materials educators use to facilitate learning and aid the needs of the learners. It plays a vital role in achieving their goals and objectives; these materials can help in how we instill knowledge in children, such as concrete, printed materials, and educational videos that are downloadable on the internet.

Teacher's use of Printed Materials as strategy

The majority of teachers stated that the strategies they used to overcome the challenges in teachers' resources were with the help of printed materials. Through this, the learner's attention will be directly focused on the teacher, and it will help the children easily understand the topic they teach.

Teachers' use of Concrete Materials as strategy

The teachers answered that having concrete materials during class discussion will help the children to analyze the lesson and familiarize themselves with the object you have given them. It can also give ideas to the learners on what the actual look of a certain object will be.

Using internet to access educational materials as strategy

The respondents highlighted that internet access plays a vital role in making their teaching materials because the materials they use for their teaching are downloaded from the internet. In this way, internet access helps them provide the materials to the learners.

Communication and collaboration

Relationships can be built and strengthened through communication (Shonkoff & Phillips, 2000). Communication and collaboration are important in making connections to help the school and the teachers achieve their goals and objectives. Communicating with the people involved makes it easier and less burdensome for the teachers to achieve their goal. Part of communicating about the concern is having PTA/GPTA meetings giving a solicitation letter to seek help from other organizations and stakeholders, even the parents of the learners.

Teacher's strategy in Communicating with parents, LGUs, community

Most of the teachers' respondents answered that communicating with parents, LGUs, and the community are their strategies to ask for help in aiding the resources they need for the learners in their study.

Conclusions

Conclusion to Research Question 1

This research holds implications for early childhood education teachers, providing their insights on how the challenges that are associated with teachers' resources in early childhood education in terms of access to educational materials and partnership and collaboration.

Based on the findings of this study, the selected early childhood education teachers in one of Zamboanga City's district schools faced multifaceted and significant challenges related to teachers' resources in early childhood education in terms of access to educational materials. The most significant of these challenges is widespread lack of access to educational materials, making it difficult to provide a high-quality education to young students. Financial constraints also were present, preventing resource acquisition. Furthermore, technological challenges hindered effective integration into teaching practices, particularly for seasoned teachers.

Additionally, this study also highlighted the challenges of teachers' resources in terms of partnership and collaboration. Fear of embarrassment and communication barriers limited opportunities for additional assistance from parents and other stakeholders, those who had positive collaboration experiences emphasized the importance of community support, particularly contributions from barangay leaders and parents. Nonetheless, negotiating parental perceptions and establishing effective communication channels were identified as critical steps in closing resource gaps and improving student learning outcomes.

Conclusion to Research Question 2

The challenges regarding teachers' resources, particularly in accessing educational materials and partnership and collaboration, are common especially in early childhood education. Nonetheless, teachers used different strategies to overcome these challenges in a diverse and effective way.

Based on the findings or based on the result of the study the challenges associated with teachers' resources in early childhood education in terms of access to educational materials. Teachers are utilizing different strategies such as accessing the technology or online platforms, also using printed and concrete materials like books, as well as engaging in collaborative learning and discussions. Also, teachers in the study are asking for help with their colleagues who are more expert and knowledgeable enough. It also mentioned that they are utilizing the gradual release of responsibility (GRR), and self-supporting just to aid things in accessing educational materials. These kinds of strategies not only aid things in accessing educational materials but also it benefits the teacher to have more effective teaching practices, making lessons easier and more effective to deliver and enhance the students' learning outcomes.

In conclusion with the challenges associated with teachers' resources in early childhood education in terms of partnerships and collaboration. Teachers used the parent-teacher association (PTA) meetings and solicitation letters as their strategies to engage and seek help or support with the external stakeholders.

Collaborating with the parents, local governments, private institutions, and community establishments is very crucial and important in addressing resource gaps. Even though financial constraints and technology can make things difficult, when teachers and communities are working together well, it really helps the school and learning environment to be better and a safe place for learning.

This research holds implications for early childhood teachers, in relation to their insights about what are the strategies used to overcome

challenges about teachers' resources in terms of access to educational materials and partnership and collaboration was determined in response to research problem 2.

This research makes the following recommendations for Curriculum developers, school administrators, early childhood teachers, pre-service teachers, early childhood education learners, and future researchers.

Curriculum Developers

Curriculum developers must ensure that all materials are easy to access and enough to provide the kind of learning system that the students should have. Also, they must collaborate with technology experts that help develop digital platforms for accessing different educational materials to better enhance the teaching and learning process of both students and teachers.

School Administrators

School administrators must ensure the smoothness and stability of the implementation of the school system by monitoring the office inventory such as the materials needed in teaching, managing an office by investing the right resources, as well as scheduling meetings to meet the common goals for children, and supervising teachers and other personnel that helps them to refine their skills and flexibility to adapt methods that meet the needs of the students.

Early Childhood Teachers

All teachers must intensify the use of different strategies to effectively deal with the challenges when it comes to learning resources (ex. not enough books, no technologies, time consuming on preparing and searching for available resources). Teachers must provide a wide range of activities that would cater to the needs of the students with or without the existence of the other resources.

Future Researchers

The research instrument of this study is limited to interview only the public school early childhood teachers. In regards to this, the researchers must utilize other instruments perhaps considering also the private

Teachers' adaptability and flexibility in seeking solutions are very crucial especially in overcoming resource challenges as well as meeting students' needs effectively. This study also acknowledges the support of the community, most particularly to the contribution coming from barangay leaders and parents, it plays a vital role especially in bridging the gap in resources as well as in improving students learning outcomes.

This study shows that establishing effective communication channels and engaging with parents that have different perceptions are a very critical way especially in strengthening the connection with the collaboration that you made and having enough resources that caters to the needs of the learners. Partnering and collaborating with other organizations or internal and external stakeholders are very important especially in an institution, because this is the way that you can do to have a better outcome in whatever you are doing. It made all the impossible works possible, and also made the work easier and achievable. Even all those big institutions or companies are still making partnerships and collaborations all throughout their journeys, because they know that it will benefit not only their institutions but also individually, that leads to a better and a successful outcome.

References

- Asasher. (2022, December 16). Issues in early childhood education in 2022. CCEI is a Straighter Line Company.
- Ascione, L. (2024, March 18). 5 educators share insights into teaching and learning. eSchool News.
- Auld, S., & Auld, S. (2023, December 6). What is the role of parents in education? ACC Blog.
- Bantilan, J. C., Hatagi, M. C. A., Sombilon, E. J. J., & Bauyot, M. M. (2023). Financial management challenges and strategies of public secondary school leaders in Davao City, Philippines: A phenomenological multiple case study. *Journal of Education, Society and Behavioural Science*, 36(12), 131–158.
- Carvalho, L., Nicholson, T., Yeoman, P., & Thibaut, P. (2020). Space matters: Framing the New Zealand learning landscape. *Learning Environments Research*, 23(3), 307–329.
- CNN Philippines. (2023, August 23). The cost of classroom overcrowding and lack of learning resources | New Day [Video]. YouTube.
- College Values Online. (2022, November 4). 7 challenges and opportunities for early childhood education teachers.
- December, M. L. P. I. P. I. (2023b, December 12). Parental involvement - pedagogue. *Pedagogue*.
- De Freitas Langrafe, T., Barakat, S. R., Stocker, F., & Boaventura, J. M. G. (2020). A stakeholder theory approach to creating value in higher education institutions. *The Bottom Line: Managing Library Finances*, 33(4), 297–313.
- DepEd Cavite Research. (2022, May 26). External stakeholders' participation on programs & activity development in the improvement of education [Video]. YouTube.

- Doğan, S., Dogan, N., & Çelik, İ. (2020). Teachers' skills to integrate technology in education: Two path models explaining instructional and application software use. *Education and Information Technologies*, 26(1), 1311–1332.
- Due.com. (n.d.). Lack of resources causes underdeveloped learning generationally. Nasdaq.
- Educational challenges in the Philippines. (n.d.).
- Educational challenges in the Philippines. (n.d.-a).
- Effects of lack of resource materials for students | Bartleby. (n.d.).
- Family and community partnerships in education. (n.d.). Obo.
- Fernandez, A. A., & Shaw, G. P. (2020). Academic leadership in a time of crisis: The coronavirus and COVID-19. *Journal of Leadership Studies*, 14(1), 39–45.
- Financial management challenges and strategies of public secondary school leaders in Davao City, Philippines: A phenomenological multiple case study - OA Open Library. (n.d.).
- Fyall, A., Garrod, B., & Wang, Y. (2012). Destination collaboration: A critical review of theoretical approaches to a multi-dimensional phenomenon. *Journal of Destination Marketing and Management*, 1(1–2), 10–26.
- George, N. (2006). Breaking the learning barrier for underachieving students: Practical teaching strategies for dramatic results. GGI Insights. (2023, October 24). Challenges facing early childhood education: Key issues and solutions. Sustainability.
- Howley-Rouse, A. (2023, September 19). Common partnership challenges and how to address them. The Education Hub.
- IRResearch. (n.d.). The impact of school budgeting on teachers' performance.
- İşler, O. (2021). Resource scarcity. In Springer eBooks (pp. 6647–6649).
- Learning and teaching materials | Unesco IIEP Learning Portal. (n.d.-b).
- Main, P. (2023, January 24). Teaching and learning strategies: A classroom guide. Structural Learning.
- Main, P. (2023a, January 26). Experiential learning. Structural Learning.
- Maffea, J. (n.d.). Lack of resources in classrooms. Research Commons at Kutztown University.
- Marketing. (2023, August 7). Why is early childhood education important? National University.
- Meador, D. (2019, February 18). 7 factors that make teaching so challenging. ThoughtCo.
- OLCreate. (n.d.). General teaching methods: Purpose of teaching and learning materials. OLCreate.
- Paccaud, A., Keller, R., Luder, R., Pastore, G., & Kunz, A. (2021). Satisfaction with the collaboration between families and schools – The parent's view. *Frontiers in Education*, 6.
- Palatino, M. (2023, February 22). The Philippines' basic education crisis. The Diplomat.
- Patton, A. (2023, June 5). Andy Patton on LinkedIn: #enfuce #collaboration #fintech #innovation #partnerships #futureoffinance.
- Penfold, L. (n.d.). Material matters in children's creative learning. ResearchGate.
- Posts, V. M. (2023, June 9). The benefit of instructional material to final year students. Uniprojectmaterials.
- Preschool, S. J. (2023, August 31). Which problems are faced in early childhood education?
- Resource constraints | Pacific Islands Literacy & Numeracy Assessment. (2023, May 8). Pacific Islands Literacy & Numeracy Assessment.
- Safeopedia, W. I. R. S.-D. F. (2018, August 11). Resource scarcity. Safeopedia.com.
- Senibulu, I. (2010). Fiji. In Elsevier eBooks (pp. 563–568).
- Shamblin, S. R., Graham, D., & Bianco, J. A. (2016). Creating trauma-informed schools for rural Appalachia: The partnerships program for enhancing resiliency, confidence, and workforce development in early childhood education. *School Mental Health*, 8(1), 189–200.
- Suleiman, Y., Adeniyi, S. T., Kamal, O., Oluwaseun, L. S., & Abiodun, O. M. (n.d.). An assessment of students' enrolment rate in University of Ilorin, Nigeria from 2019-2021: Implications for management. Digital Commons@Lindenwood University.
- The importance of accessible learning materials. (n.d.). Education Links.

The role of teachers and parents: A shared responsibility. (2022, July 25). DepEd - Nueva Ecija.

The role of teaching and learning materials and interaction as a tool to quality early childhood education in Agona East District of the Central Region of Ghana. (2021). *African Educational Research Journal*, 9(1), 2354–2160.

Teaching and learning resources – Selecting appropriate materials: Policy. (n.d.). Education.vic.gov.au.

Trainer, T. (2019, November 2). Teaching with limited resources: Challenges and potential benefits. TEFL.

Tutt, P. (2021, July 30). Teacher-parent communication strategies to start the year off right. Edutopia.

What are educational partnerships? (n.d.). IGI Global.

What are the effects of a lack of resources in teaching in the Philippines? | 5 answers from research papers. (n.d.-b.). SciSpace - Question.

What is preparation in teaching and why is it important? (n.d.).

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